

PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN TEACHING WRITING RECOUNT TEXT

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Abstract: Writing recount text, therefore, is very important for students to master since it develops students' writing skill in delivering chronological information. This skill later, will be needed in higher education or in university. In writing recount text, students will deliver information in the sequence of: the introduction, the sequences of information and the conclusion students will work in team and support each other in the project. Students will think more complex rather than writing a simple text in the learning. Thus, project based learning is considered as a learning strategy for teaching writing.

Key words: PBL, Writing, Recount text

INTRODUCTION

Recount text is a text to retell experiences in the past (Anderson, 1997). Writing recount text, therefore, is very important for students to master since it develops students' writing skill in delivering chronological information. This skill later, will be needed in higher education or in university. In writing recount text, students will deliver information in the sequence of: the introduction, the sequences of information and the conclusion (Anderson, 1997). In more detail, orientation leads to general information such subjects, place and time, while sequence of events leads to chronological information from the

first event to the last in series. Re-orientation leads students to give a conclusion for the whole information in a point (Anderson, 1997).

In Indonesian curriculum, Recount text was determined as a text genre and should be taught and learned in high school, specifically as a core and basic competence for the tenth graders. It is stated that students should be able to comprehend and compose simple oral and written recount text based on the social function, text structure and language features based on context (Ministry of Education Regulation No.59, 2014 about Core Competence and Basic Competence). Therefore, it is mandated for teachers to build students’ recount text writing skills.

However, some English teachers in Indonesia still consider writing as a skill which is not tested in the national examination (Hernawati, 2015). As a result, this decision would affect students’ skill in writing because students get limited writing allotment. This condition also depicted in the research by Pratomo (2014) who observed that the teacher provided limited writing opportunity. In addition to that, Pratomo (2014) also reported that the limited activity provided are demotivating and therefore, decrease students’ learning motivation.

Limited writing allotment and students’ low motivation are not the only challenges in writing classes in Indonesia. Larasati (2015) wrote that the learning strategy was ineffective since teachers implement the direct Indonesian-English translation method. As the effect, students get demotivated and could not develop their skill. These writing challenges then added to the negative perception of the students on writing makes writing class, although important, but show little significance in improving students’ skill (Chikita, Padmadewi, & Suarnajaya, 2013). Therefore, teachers need to provide more interesting activities, a

contextual topic which is close to students' daily life and give motivation for students to improve their writing skill.

Due to the significance of recount text for students to master yet challenges both from the side of the students and the teachers were reported, urgent needs for a more effective instructional strategy is irrefutable. One of the solution in teaching writing recount text is to equip students with various sources of information students can get (Sciamarelli, 2010). Moreover, if the methodology applied in learning the recount text is project based learning, and that it is based on students' real life, Lystiana (2016) stated that it will help students to write better because students can relate it closely with the writing text and because students can share their idea, creativity and imagination. All in all, project based learning methodology may also resolve the challenge of students' boredom and low motivation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Recount text is a text to retell experiences in the past (Anderson, 1997). Writing recount text, therefore, is very important for students to master since it develops students' writing skill in delivering chronological information. This skill later, will be needed in higher education or in university. In writing recount text, students will deliver information in the sequence of: the introduction, the sequences of information and the conclusion (Anderson, 1997). In more detail, orientation leads to general information such subjects, place and time, while sequence of events leads to chronological information from the first event to the last in series. Re-orientation leads students to give a conclusion for the whole information in a point (Anderson, 1997).

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Different to the other learning methods which provide limited activity for students, project based learning is students-centered which provides more activities (Liao, ____). In the teaching writing, it means that students will get more writing allotment in the learning. It also allows students to discuss, plan and compose a project in their writing activity (Thitivesa, 2014). Moreover, Larasati (2014) stated that students will work in team and support each other in the project. Students will think more complex rather than writing a simple text in the learning. Thus, project based learning is considered as a learning strategy for teaching writing.

Micro- and Macro-skills of Writing

The basis of writing assessment is the micro and macro skills of writing. They will be the criteria decided by the teacher to be assessed as a good writing. Brown (2008) has compiled the micro and macro skills of writing as follows.

Micro-skills

- 1) Producing graphemes and orthographic pattern of English.
- 2) Producing writing at an efficient rate of speed to suit the purpose.

3) Producing an acceptable core of words and use appropriate word order patterns.

4) Using grammatical system (e.g., tense, agreement, and pluralization, patterns, and rules).

5) Expressing a particular meaning in different grammatical forms.

6) Using cohesive devices in written discourse.

7) Using the rhetorical forms and conventions of written discourse.

Macro-skills

8) Accomplishing appropriately the communicative functions of written text according to form and purpose.

9) Conveying links and connections between events and communicate such relations as main idea, supporting idea, new information, given information, generalization, and exemplification. Distinguishing between literal and implied meanings when writing.

10) Correctly conveying culturally specific references in the context of the writing text.

11) Developing and using a battery of writing strategies, such as accurately assessing the audience’s interpretation, using prewriting devices, writing with fluency in the first drafts, using paraphrases and synonyms, soliciting peer and instructor feedback, and using feedback for revising and editing.

The researcher does not take all of the micro and macro skills given above. He will only take as he needs to achieve the standard of writing in the school and the national education. It is including the grammatical system (4), rhetorical forms and conventions of written discourse (7), communicative function of written text according to form and purpose (8) and conveying links and connection between events (9). These criteria were also used by Pearson (2012) in Kentucky education department to assess writing. It includes the idea, organization, words choice and sentence structure.

Writing Performances

There are four categories of written performance which are captured from the range of written production (Brown, 2007). This will be used by teacher to decide the level of the writing produced by the students. Teacher will consider the target of the writing task by those performances. Those are listed as the followings:

2.1.1 Imitative

It is the basic and fundamental skill of writing. The students are focused on writing letters, words, punctuation and very brief sentences. At this level of performance, the writing form is the primary, while meaning and context is secondary concern.

2.1.2 Intensive

It also called as controlled writing. In the imitative writing, students focus on the vocabulary, spelling and other basics. Here students start the essential meaning of their writing where the context is considered. But they need to be guided as the beginner.

2.1.3 Responsive

While creating a sentence with single context and meaning, responding another meaning of writing seems like a higher level of writing communication. Students respond the context and produce the responding context. This level could reach the paragraphs composing. And strong meaning has been the attention.

2.1.4 Extensive

Extensive writing implies the management of writing kinds of text for all purpose. Students started to elaborate the idea systematically in the writing types, such as essay, project report, daily story or even a thesis. Purpose, developing idea, organization and other specific aspects are being the focus in this level.

By those writing performances, researcher will only apply the extensive writing which presents higher target for the students to produce the writing. It also trains them to organize their writing independently, widely and chronologically based on their experience. In the process of the learning writing activity, extensive writing engages in the process of multiple drafts to achieve a final project (Brown, 2007). Thus, the extensive writing will be very suitable for the Project-Based Learning which is also process-oriented.

Moreover, the focus of extensive writing which is achieving purpose, developing idea, and organizing the writing will make students able to explore their selves. Supported by specific topic which is close to the students’ daily live, students will be more help to develop their writing wider. Therefore, having a specific topic in extensive writing is very helpful in students’ writing process.

Project-Based Learning Process

Project based learning can be understood as a learner-centered teaching approach which focuses on the process or efforts (Marwan, 2015). There are different steps of project-based learning in its development, but The George Lucas Educational Foundation (2005, cited in Larasati, 2015) gives a more detailed procedure of project-based learning which is appropriate for this study. There are some procedures to achieve the product in project-based based learning. The followings are the procedures of project-based learning:

a. Start with the essential question

This step is aimed to give the students essential question which leads the students to the project. The teacher starts the learning by giving the material then provides an essential question which relevant and they should achieve during the project learning. The question must be related to the students’ background knowledge and their real-daily life.

b. Design a plan for the project

In this step, the teacher gives chance to the students to be involved in designing the project. They may share their idea about the project. It deals with the students’ interest, capability and capability to accomplish the project. The

discussions will be also regarding about the topic, schedule, dividing jobs and presentation procedure.

c. Create a schedule

Following the previous step, the teacher and the students should discuss the time allotment in doing the project. They should have an agreement about the step schedule, the deadline and the consequence.

d. Monitor the students and the progress of the project

This step is the most crucial step which teacher should be a facilitator for the students' project progress. The teacher should monitor and facilitate for each difficulties faced by the students. It is also the moment when teacher assess students affective towards the project doing whether they are involved well or not in the project.

e. Assess the outcome

The assessment would be the teacher job as the students have been working during the project doing. The teacher may assess the students' final project (project oriented) or even the process of the project doing (process oriented). This will show the students' achievement in their project. The teacher also gives feedback for the students in this step.

f. Evaluate the experience

The evaluation would be the last step of the project-based learning which the teacher and the students will evaluate the project they have done. The teacher and the students try to find the strength and the weaknesses on the project so that they can improve it in the next project. In this step also, students will share their experience in their process of doing project.

Recount Text

A Recount text is a type of oral or written text which purposed to retell the listener or readers about the past experiences, history or even activity report. It also requires orientation, the sequence of events and reorientation. In school context, The Department of Education and Communities in New South Wales

(2011) stated that recount text retells events which have already happened in the past; it begins with background information, describes the series of events chronologically and may end with a personal conclusion or comment. We could find recount text in some fiction or non-fiction novel, biography or even dairy book.

2.4.1 Generic Structure

There are three points of text structure of recount text based on Mark and Kathy Anderson (1997 and 2003) which is used as the reference for many English learning textbooks. Those are:

1. Orientation

As one part of recount text, Orientation introduces the participants, place and time of the story. This part will gives background information to the reader about who, where and when is the story happened.

2. Events

This part of text describes the series of event that happened in the past. As we call it series, we may deliver it in sequence whether it is front, back or flashback. Or even we deliver it chronologically.

3. Reorientation

This last part states a conclusion and personal comment of the writer to the story. What they feel or think after the experience? We may also call this part as conclusion of the story. After all, this part is optional.

2.4.2 Language Features

1. Introducing personal participant: I, my group, my family

2. Using linking verb: was, were, saw

3. Using action verb (past form): looked, went, changed, ran

4. Using simple past tenses: I went to the field, We ran from the buffalo

5. Using chronological conjunction: then, first, after that

Conclusion

Project-based learning presents both process-oriented and product-oriented learning (Stoller, 1997 cited in Pramoto, 2014). It means that there will be a

process of writing to achieve a product as the target. Teachers will give a process in writing a project of recount text. Recount text is a chronological text which needs a process to make a perfect of it. Hernawati (2014) also conduct a study about project-based learning in writing recount text in Junior High School. Its finding showed that project-based learning could improve students' writing competence in recount text. Moreover, the students could achieve 280 words in their recount text. Thus, the researcher confidently wants to apply project-based learning in recount text to improve students' writing competence in recount text.

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